

Phylogenetic and functional characterization of water bears (Tardigrada) tubulins

Kamila Novotná Floriančíčová^{1,3,#}, Athanasios Baltzis^{2,#}, Jiří Smejkal³, Michaela Czerneková¹, Łukasz Kaczmarek⁴, Jan Malý³, Cedric Notredame^{2,5} & Stanislav Vinopal^{1,3,*}

¹Department of Biology, Faculty of Science, J. E. Purkyně University (UJEP), Usti nad Labem, Czech Republic

²Centre for Genomic Regulation, Barcelona, Spain

³Centre for Nanotechnology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Science, UJEP, Usti nad Labem, Czech Republic

⁴Department of Animal Taxonomy and Ecology, Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Poznań, Poland

⁵Universitat Pompeu Fabra (UPF), Barcelona, Spain

#These authors contributed equally

*Corresponding author

ABSTRACT

Tardigrades are microscopic ecdysozoans that can withstand extreme environmental conditions. Several tardigrade species undergo reversible morphological transformations and enter into cryptobiosis that helps them to survive periods of unfavourable environmental conditions. However, underlying molecular mechanisms of cryptobiosis are mostly unknown. Tubulins are evolutionarily conservative components of the microtubule cytoskeleton that play crucial roles in many cellular processes. We hypothesize that microtubules are necessary for morphological changes associated with successful cryptobiosis. Molecular composition of microtubule cytoskeleton in tardigrades is unknown. Therefore, we analyzed and characterized tardigrade tubulins. We identified 79 tardigrade tubulin sequences in eight taxa. We found three α -tubulin and seven β -tubulin isoforms, one γ -tubulin and one ϵ -tubulin isoform. To verify *in silico* identified tardigrade tubulins, we also isolated and sequenced 9 out of 10 predicted *Hypsibius exemplaris* tubulins. All tardigrade tubulins were localized as expected: to the microtubules or to the centrosomes when overexpressed in mammalian cultured cells. The presence of a functional ϵ -tubulin, clearly localized to centrioles, is interesting from a phylogenetic point of view. Although phylogenetically close Nematoda lost their δ - and ϵ -tubulin, some groups of Arthropoda still possess them. Thus, our data support the current placement of tardigrades to Panarthropoda.

Keywords: cytoskeleton, microtubules, tardigrades, tubulin

INTRODUCTION

Tardigrades, also called water bears, are microscopic ecdysozoans that belong to the phylum Tardigrada, which is divided into three classes: well-defined Heterotardigrada, Eutardigrada, and dubious Mesotardigrada¹. Tardigrades are known for their unique ability to withstand extreme environmental conditions like desiccation, vacuum, low/high temperature, and radiation. Several tardigrade species undergo reversible morphological transformations (formation of tuns) and enter into cryptobiosis that helps them to survive periods of unfavourable environmental conditions²⁻⁹. However, underlying molecular mechanisms have only begun to emerge¹⁰⁻¹⁴.

The phylogenetic position of the phylum Tardigrada is discussed, some authors suggested that tardigrades are part of animal clade Panarthropoda (euarthropods and onychophorans)¹⁵⁻¹⁸, others suggested a closer phylogenetic relationship between Tardigrada and Nematoda than between Tardigrada and Arthropoda¹⁹. Despite an increasing amount of molecular evidence, tardigrade phylogeny has remained unresolved.

A system for cellular movement and changes in shape is provided by the cytoskeleton. It consists of three major protein filaments families - actin filaments, intermediate filaments and microtubules. Each type of cytoskeletal filaments has different mechanical properties, dynamics, and biological roles, however, the systems are interrelated²⁰.

Interestingly, Panarthropoda generally possess microtubules, and actin filaments but lack cytoplasmic intermediate filaments (IFs)²¹. The loss of cytoplasmic IFs in the arthropod lineage may be caused by the presence of an exoskeleton^{21,22} which provides mechanical support. In tardigrades, the cytoplasmic role of IFs was substituted by a novel lamin-derived protein Cytotardin²³. Cytotardin does not form

scaffold-like structures throughout the cell but belt-like filaments²³. Cytotardin was found in the epidermis and tissues exposed to mechanical stress and therefore might help to resist extreme conditions²³.

Microtubules are hollow cylinders composed of evolutionarily conserved heterodimers of tubulin proteins and play critical roles in many cellular processes²⁴. Tardigrade microtubules were observed in an electron microscopic study in claw glands²⁵ and also in recent studies on tardigrade nervous system^{16,26–32}.

We hypothesize that microtubules might play an important role in tardigrade physiology and are necessary for morphological changes associated with cryptobiosis. The molecular composition of the microtubule cytoskeleton in tardigrades is unknown. Therefore, we decided to start elucidating this outstanding question by analyzing and characterizing tardigrade tubulins.

RESULTS

To study the molecular composition of tardigrade microtubule cytoskeleton, we had to identify and analyze tardigrade tubulin coding sequences (CDS). We used published transcriptomes and genomes (with annotated predicted CDS) of eight tardigrade taxa (Table 1). We generated three datasets of putative tardigrade tubulin homologs based on full length sequences and tubulin domains (UJEP dataset, CRG dataset, CRG tubulin domains dataset; see Methods). We ran regressive T-coffee³³ alignments of found tardigrade tubulin protein sequences together with a large dataset published by Findeisen et al.³⁴ that contains 3524 tubulin or tubulin-like sequences from 504 species (Supplementary data 1).

To estimate which tubulin isotypes and isoforms we found in tardigrades, we constructed phylogenetic trees based on the alignments. We used maximum likelihood

(IQ-TREE) and minimum evolution (FastME) methods. All phylogenetic trees were always rooted in Archea tubulin-like sequences. The tardigrade tubulins that we found clustered into α -, β -, γ - and ϵ -tubulin isotypes (Fig. 1, Supplementary data 2; for unification of nomenclature see Supplementary Table S1). Of note, we adopted simplified tubulin naming from Findeisen et al.³⁴, where Greek letters were substituted by numbers (e.g., α -tubulin is Tub1, β -tubulin is Tub2 etc.).

This analysis allowed us to identify several divergent non-tubulin (tPr-orf74 and tPr-GFGY01000052.1x) and putatively non-tardigrade sequences that we removed manually from the final dataset. For example, *Paramacrobiotus richtersi* (Murray, 1911) sequences *tPr-orf110*, *tPr-orf67*, *tPr-orf77* exhibited 87 %, 87 % and 61% identity, respectively, to tubulins in *Nematocida displodere* Luallen, Reinke, Tong, Botts, Félix & Troemel, 2016³⁵ that is a natural microsporidian parasite of *Caenorhabditis elegans*. Of note, carnivorous *Pam. richtersi* can be fed on *C. elegans*, so these sequences are likely contamination. We further removed several additional truncated sequences that were identical to longer protein sequences from the same taxa present in the dataset (Supplementary Table S1).

The curated final dataset was aligned to Findeisen et al.³⁴ tubulin dataset using the regressive mode of T-Coffee³³. This alignment served as a template for computation of the final phylogenetic tree (Fig. 2a, Supplementary data 3) using maximum-likelihood method (IQ-TREE). The tardigrade tubulins clustered into α -, β -, γ - and ϵ -tubulin isotypes similarly as before. Moreover, we were able to distinguish individual isoforms inside the tubulin isotype clusters based on detailed manual sequence analysis (Fig. 2b, Supplementary data 3).

In total, we found three α -tubulin and seven β -tubulin isoforms, one γ - and one ϵ -tubulin isoform (Supplementary Table S1). Based on sequence analysis, we suspect

that tEs-orf27 might be another example of contamination. It exhibits 75 % identity to *Pollicipes pollicipes*, a barnacle where *Echiniscoides s. sigismundi* (M. Schultze, 1865) is often collected³⁶.

We determined three α -isoforms that we named Tub1A1, Tub1A2 and Tub1C1. In Tub1A1, the C-terminal tyrosine residue is replaced by valine. The Tub1A2 seems to have a relatively similar C-terminus to vertebrate α -tubulins. The Tub1C1 possesses C-terminal tyrosine or rarely phenylalanine however it lacks conserved previous double glutamate (Fig. 3, Supplementary data 4).

We found seven β -tubulin isoforms that had relatively diverse C-termini when compared to α -tubulins (Fig. 4, Supplementary data 4). While Tub2A isoform from *Echiniscus testudo* (Doyère, 1840) is clearly distant from other tardigrade β -tubulin isoforms, the other isoforms share relatively high degree of similarity, including the heterotardigrade Tub2D4 isoform from *Ech. testudo* and from *Ecn. s. sigismundi*. The presence of a conserved hydrophobic aminoacid (AA) at the relative position 371 in Tub2C isoform is interesting. Non-polar AA at this position are conserved in many β III-tubulins in vertebrates and in some invertebrates^{37,38} suggesting Tub2C might be a β III-tubulin homolog.

The γ -tubulin and ϵ -tubulin were found as single isoforms in analyzed tardigrade genomes and transcriptomes (Supplementary data 4) with two exceptions. However, it is likely that the truncated version of *Ech. testudo* γ -tubulin (tEt-orf155, 304 AA) translated *in silico* from an alternative start codon corresponds to the full length *Ech. testudo* γ -tubulin (tEt-orf155, 526 AA). Two ϵ -tubulin sequences from *Ecn. s. sigismundi* (orf187 and orf188; Supplementary data 4) also seem to be fragments of one ϵ -tubulin sequence, corresponding to N- and C-terminal parts, respectively.

However, this must be proven by direct isolation and sequencing of the CDS from *Ecn. s. sigismundi* specimens in the future.

To verify the function of found tubulin sequences we aimed at isolating the identified tubulin CDS from tardigrades and express them in mammalian cells (for the lack of robust molecular tools for expression directly in tardigrades). We isolated 9 out of 10 annotated tubulins from *Hypsibius exemplaris* Gąsiorek, Stec, Morek & Michalczyk, 2018³⁹ (Supplementary Table S2); the exception was Tub2D5 (Genebank OWA50044.1) that we were not able to amplify despite trying different primer pairs (Supplementary Table S3). Translated protein sequences from isolated tubulin CDS were almost identical to previously annotated versions (few single AA changes reflecting likely intra-species diversity), with the exception of γ -tubulin (Supplementary Table S2).

Interestingly, the length of the previously annotated γ -tubulin was 912 AA (Genebank OQV14445.1; Supplementary Table S2). In the large dataset including thousands of eukaryotic tubulins³⁴ and also among other tardigrade γ -tubulins, there were no γ -tubulins of similar length. We suspected a probable mistake in assigning exon-intron boundaries. This is why we analyzed the whole coding sequence in the contig (Genebank MTYJ01000105.1). Sequence analysis using NetGene2^{40,41} predicting splice sites revealed by using *C. elegans* settings (*C. elegans* belongs to Ecdysozoa as tardigrades) that the putative donor splice site at the boundary of the exon 4 was dubious. The NetGene2 predicted an alternative splice site further downstream. We modified the coding sequence by adding the putative intronic sequence following the annotated exon 4 until the newly predicted donor splice site (CTGAGCAAAG); this modification gave rise to a stop codon in frame in the added sequence. Based on this adjustment, we designed a reverse primer downstream of the stop codon

(Supplementary Table S3) and successfully amplified a functional γ -tubulin from the adult *Hys. exemplaris* cDNA.

All tardigrade β -tubulin isoforms tagged with mScarlet fluorescent protein localized properly to microtubules (Fig. 5a-5b) that were labelled by α -tubulin from human (EGFP-TUBA1B). The mEGFP-tagged tardigrade α -tubulins localized to microtubules as well as verified by coexpression with tardigrade β -tubulins (Fig. 5c). In general, tardigrade β -tubulins were more easily detected on mammalian microtubules than tardigrade α -tubulins. The weakest microtubule localization was observed with tHe-Tub1A2. This tardigrade tubulin was mostly diffuse, however, some microtubule localizations were detectable (Fig. 5c). The expected subcellular localization was observed also for tardigrade γ - and ϵ -tubulin. Both of these isotypes localized to the centrosomes in human hTert-RPE-1 cells (Fig. 5c). To conclude, all isolated tardigrade tubulins localized to expected subcellular locations.

DISCUSSION

Here we have found that tardigrades possess four tubulin isotypes that function similarly to their vertebrate counterparts. The identification of functional ϵ -tubulin in the eutardigrade *Hys. exemplaris* and its presence also in heterotardigrades argues for the phylogenetic placement of all tardigrades among Panarthropoda.

Eukaryotic tubulins belong to six major subfamilies (α , β , γ , δ , ϵ , ζ) and the last common ancestor of Eukaryota probably had all six tubulin isotypes^{34,42}. We found 23 α -, 43 β -, 9 γ - and 3 ϵ -tubulin sequences in tardigrades. The number of β -tubulins is generally higher than α -tubulins^{34,43} and this trend was also observed here in tardigrades. Notably, tubulin sequences from *Ech. testudo* and *Milnesium t. tardigradum* Doyère, 1840 (newly *Milnesium inceptum* Morek, Suzuki, Schill,

Georgiev, Yankova, Marley & Michalczyk, 2019⁴⁴) were mostly truncated which might reflect the poorer quality of the available sequencing data. It is likely that other tardigrade tubulin proteins could still be found with improved transcriptomic, genomic and proteomic approaches in future, especially in the above-mentioned species.

We found three tardigrade α -tubulin isoforms: Tub1A1, Tub1A2 and Tub1C1. Interestingly, Tub1A1 and Tub1A2 cluster comprises both Hetero- and Eutardigrada sequences indicating that these isoforms were likely present in the last common tardigrade ancestor. The other isoform (Tub1C1) might be a gene duplication that occurred later during evolution. However, fragmented and truncated tubulin sequences found in analyzed heterotardigrade transcriptomes make it hard to draw a more definitive conclusion.

The isoform Tub1A1 does not have the C-terminal tyrosine residue (-EEV). The Tub1C1 possesses C-terminal tyrosine or rarely phenylalanine, however, it lacks the conserved predecesing double glutamate (-NGEY/F). The question is whether Tub1A1 and Tub1C1 can undergo the classical tyrosination and detyrosination cycle that is typical for the majority of α -tubulins across many species²⁴. On the other hand, all found tardigrade α -tubulins possess a lysine residue equivalent to vertebrate Lys40 that is a target for acetylation²⁴. Indeed, anti-acetylated tubulin antibody was successfully used in studies on tardigrade nervous system^{16,26}.

Tardigrade β -tubulin sequences formed seven clusters, many of which reflected class or order distinction of respective taxa. The Tub2D2s from the order Apochela (Tub2D2-Apo) were separated from the other eutardigrades (Tub2D2-Eu). The Tub2D4 sequences were split based on the membership to the class Eutardigrada or Heterotardigrada, Tub2D4-Eu or Tub2D4-Het, respectively. The Tub2D3, Tub2C and Tub2A formed independent clusters, with Tub2A being the most distant. Despite the

fact that all sequences in this cluster are truncated, their sequence signature is distinct from the other clusters which justifies the existence of this *Ech. testudo*-specific isoform.

C-termini of tardigrade β -tubulins are more diverse in comparison to α -tubulins and it was difficult to find some conserved sequences.

An interesting isoform is Tub2C which might be a homolog of vertebrate β III-tubulins which are expressed primarily in neurons and in certain cancer cells³⁷. We base our interpretation on the presence of a hydrophobic AA at the relative position AA371 in our alignment (in the literature on vertebrate tubulins designated as AA351). There is a polar threonine change to a non-polar isoleucine or valine which is conserved in many β III-tubulins in vertebrates and even invertebrates^{37,38}. Interestingly, the highly extremotolerant *Ramazzottius varieornatus* Bertolani & Kinchin, 1993⁴⁵ lacks Tub2C isoform and the ϵ -tubulin as well⁴⁶.

To verify the function of tardigrade tubulins, we wanted to isolate their CDS directly from tardigrades and test them in cells. All tardigrade tubulins tagged with fluorescent proteins (mScarlet or EGFP) correctly localized to predicted subcellular locations in mammalian cells. All β -tubulins were incorporated into mammalian microtubules equally well and their presence was always easily detectable. On the contrary, tardigrade α -tubulins localized to microtubules relatively poorly. The best incorporation was detected for Tub1A1. The worst microtubule incorporation was observed for Tub1A2. This tubulin was mostly diffuse, nevertheless, some microtubule localization was detectable. The Tub1C1 was also frequently diffuse, however, after a longer expression time (> 48 hours), microtubule localization became clear.

Differences in the ability of mEGFP-tagged α -tubulins to incorporate into mammalian microtubules were surprising. It should be noted that the rest of the plasmid backbone,

including the linker between the tubulin CDS and the fluorescent protein CDS, was identical. One of the possible explanations for the differences might be C-termini heterogeneity which could have an impact on posttranslational modifications.

The dissimilar ability of individual tardigrade α -tubulins to incorporate into microtubules could also be influenced by temperature. The optimal temperature for *Hys. exemplaris* is between 10 °C to 18 °C and temperatures higher than 22 °C are already critical for survival⁴⁷. In contrast, the optimal temperature for mammalian cells used here is 37 °C. Generally, suboptimal temperature causes a decrease in rates of microtubule polymerization and depolymerization, the amount of polymer assembled before catastrophes, and the frequency of microtubule nucleation⁴⁸. However, it is interesting that tardigrade β -tubulins were not affected and this phenomenon warrants further investigation, ideally, directly in tardigrades.

The ϵ -tubulin has been identified in all eukaryotic kingdoms but has been lost independently in many clades several times³⁴. Remarkably, our data do not support the "ZED module" hypothesis stating that: "*(1) organisms that lack epsilon-tubulin always also lack delta- and zeta-tubulin and (2) organisms that have epsilon-tubulin always also have delta- and/or zeta-tubulin.*"⁴⁹. Importantly, the ZED module hypothesis was based on a much smaller dataset than that of Findeisen et al. ³⁴ that we used as a reference in our study.

Currently, tardigrades are classified in the clade Panarthropoda which is a part of the superphylum Ecdysozoa. However, the phylogenetic position of tardigrades within the Ecdysozoa has been still controversial and debated^{15–19,50}. Although tubulins are generally unsuitable for inference of phylogenetic position of species due to the high degree of tubulin (especially α - and β -tubulin) gene duplications occurring spontaneously and independently throughout the evolution³⁴, our analysis might still

contribute to the refinement of the phylogenetic position of Tardigrada. All Ecdysozoa lack ζ -tubulin³⁴. Remarkably, Nematoda also lost their δ - and ϵ -tubulin, however, some groups of Arthropoda still possess them, including Hymenoptera³⁴. We found three unique tardigrade ϵ -tubulin sequences, two in heterotardigrades, one in the eutardigrade *Hys. exemplaris*. Hence, our data indicate that the current placement of tardigrades among Panarthropoda is correct.

Interestingly, δ -, ϵ - or ζ -tubulin are not essential for functional cilia in general, since there are ciliated species lacking all of these isotypes³⁴. However, these tubulins are found in species that possess cilia where they play roles in ciliary assembly and function^{34,49,51,52}. Indeed, tardigrades possess cilia that fulfil important sensoric tasks⁵³. Investigation of the role of tardigrade ϵ -tubulin for tardigrade ciliary functions will be an interesting avenue of future research. Moreover, our work opens the way for exploration of the tardigrade tubulin code^{24,54} and its role in the fascinating survival abilities of tardigrades.

METHODS

Identification of tardigrade tubulin sequences

We collected tubulin protein sequences of four model organisms *Homo sapiens*, *Drosophila melanogaster*, *C. elegans* and *Mus musculus* from NCBI. We also acquired published genomes and transcriptomes of eight tardigrade taxa - *Ecn. cf. sigismund*⁵⁵, *Richtersius cf. coronifer*⁵⁵, *Ech. testudo*⁵⁶, *Mesobiotus philippinicus* Mapalo, Stec, Mirano-Bascos & Michalczyk, 2016^{56,57}, *Milnesium tardigradum* (Genebank GFGZ00000000.1), *Pam. richtersi* (Genebank GFGY00000000.1), *Hys. dujardini* (Doyère, 1840) (now *Hys. exemplaris*) (*Hys. dujardini* strain: Z151 Genome sequencing and assembly; (Yoshida et al. ¹⁹) and *Ram. varieornatus* (*Ram.*

varieornatus genome, (Hashimoto et al. ⁴⁶) (**Table 1**). Of note, originally, we used genome assemblies of those two strains from the website tardigrades.org, which has been discontinued. Regarding name abbreviations of tardigrade species/taxa, we followed Perry et al. ⁵⁸.

By using the BLAST+ software (Version 2.2.26+)⁵⁹, we prepared our local BLAST+ database from the above mentioned data. We ran a TBLASTN search in the local tardigrade BLAST+ database with an e-value cutoff of $1E10^{-5}$ using tubulin protein sequences from *H. sapiens*, *M. musculus*, *D. melanogaster* and *C. elegans* as a query (Supplementary Data 5). Multiplicate redundant sequences were filtered out based on unique sequence IDs. Hits with a unique sequence ID were further aligned using Clustal Omega⁶⁰ and identical redundant sequences from the same species were removed. The resulting dataset of about 90 putative tardigrade tubulin sequences was transferred to Benchling and translated based on coordinates from the BLAST+ search (frame and strand) (UJEP dataset).

Alternatively, the unique sequences were translated using esl-translate function of HMMER package esl-translate from the HMMER package and an in-house macro for trimming erroneous N-terminal AA extensions arising from artificial translation of 5' segments of identified transcripts (3.1b2 February 2015) (CRG dataset). To extract the domain sequences of the tardigrade tubulin proteins, we used hmmscan from the HMMER package with the default parameters to scan Pfam32.0 ⁶¹ and retrieved the hits corresponding to the Pfam tubulin family (PF00091.25) (CRG tubulin domains dataset).

Multiple Sequence Alignments computation and phylogenetic inference

The phylogenetic analysis was carried out in two steps. First, we computed multiple sequence alignments of the found putative tardigrade tubulin protein or domain sequences together with a previously published large tubulin protein dataset³⁴ relying on the regressive mode of Toffee³³ (Version_13.45.58.c355d11 with Clustal Omega⁶⁰ guide trees and MAFFT-G-INS-i alignments⁶²)

Second, the produced alignments were used as input to phylogenetic reconstruction tools based on maximum likelihood (IQ-TREE⁶³, version 2.1.2) and minimum evolution (FastME⁶⁴, version 2.1.6.1).

Culture of *Hys. exemplaris*

Samples of *Hys. exemplaris* were obtained from envirocom (Tübingen, Germany) and from our own culture. Eutardigrade *Hys. exemplaris* is a freshwater, herbivorous species that typically feeds on algae and was cultured as described previously⁴⁷, but with small modifications. Briefly, tardigrades were cultured on 90 mm plastic Petri dishes. The bottom of all dishes was scratched with a fine sandpaper to allow easier locomotion of tardigrades. Each dish contained 10 mL of Chalkley's medium (0.004 g/L KCl, 0.1 g/L NaCl, 0.006 g/L CaCl₂, 20 ml/L soil extract; Soil extract was an autoclaved supernatant of fertile, humus-enriched soil and distilled water in 1:2 ratio. The extract was allowed to settle over a few days and then filtered) mixed with 50 mL of spring water (Rajec, Czech Republic). Cultures were fed with green algae *Chlorococcum* sp. by adding ca. 1 volume concentrated algal culture to 4 volumes of the tardigrade culture. Each culture was checked every 2 to 3 days with a microscope to ensure tardigrades flourished and the oxygen supply was provided by pipetting. According to need, tardigrades were fed the algae every one or two weeks. During the

cleaning/checking procedures, a thin iridescent film on the surface of the medium, dead animals, old exuviae, and different organic residues were removed using the pipette. The $\frac{3}{4}$ volume of the medium was changed once every ten days. This approach has proven successful in that not all food was consumed and the medium was still fresh. In each Petri dish, the population numbered around 500 individuals. If the number of specimens became too large, juveniles and eggs were transferred to a new culture dish. Cultures were stored in a Q-Cell incubator equipped with a combined cooling and heating system with forced air circulation. The temperature was constantly set at 18.7 °C. The external light source (INVITAL LED) with a combination of white and blue LED was installed into the incubator with a 10 h/14 h (light/dark) photoperiod. Algal culture media have several components in common - sources of nitrogen, phosphorus, vitamins and trace metals. For the culture of *Chlorococcum* sp., we used Bold's Basal Medium⁶⁵ as a basis. The algae were grown in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks with the mouth covered by two layers of parafilm. The algae settled at the bottom therefore they were shaken by hand once a week. Flasks were located in the laboratory out of the direct sunlight. The laboratory room temperatures fluctuated between 20 °C and 24 °C.

Sample collection and mRNA isolation from *Hys. exemplaris* specimens

We collected adult specimens (ca. 200 µm to 300 µm in length) in their culture medium and removed various contaminating substances using a pipette. Specimens were washed several times, first with distilled water and then with ultrapure water. Tardigrades (ca. 2000 individuals) were placed in a low-retention 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tube. The tube was centrifuged at 10 000 x g for 1 minute at room temperature. During centrifugation, tardigrades sedimented at the bottom of the tube

and compacted into a visible pellet. The supernatant was carefully removed as much as possible without disrupting the pellet. In some cases, samples were flash frozen in liquid nitrogen at this stage. Otherwise, we were quickly crushing the pellet with a sterile plastic pestle for 3 seconds at room temperature and then resuspend it by adding 200 μ L of RLT buffer from the RNeasy kit (Qiagen) that contained 1 % (v/v) 2-mercaptoethanol. Then, we crushed the sample again for 5 seconds and rapidly froze it in liquid nitrogen. As a next step, we removed the tube from the liquid nitrogen and allowed the sample to thaw. As the sample started to thaw, we were crushing it again for 10 seconds. We repeated the freeze/thaw/crushing steps five times (until homogenization). At the end, we washed the pestle with 150 μ L RLT buffer with 2-mercaptoethanol. For sample homogenization, we mixed the sample five times with a 20 G syringe. We used RNeasy Mini Kit for total RNA isolation according to manufacturer's instructions. The RNA was eluted with RNase-free water. The concentration was measured by UV/VIS spectrophotometer Denovix. RNA was stored at -80 °C.

Reverse transcription

The RNA template was converted into cDNA by SuperScript® IV Reverse Transcriptase (18090010, Thermo Fisher Scientific) using oligo dT primers according to manufacturer's instructions. We used RNaseH (M0297S, NEB) to remove RNA duplexed with the newly synthesised cDNA. The cDNA was stored at -20 °C.

Cloning of tardigrade tubulin coding sequences

Individual tardigrade tubulin CDS were isolated by PCR using specific forward (fwd) and reverse (rev) primers (Supplementary Table S3) and cDNA from adult *Hys*.

exemplaris specimens as a template. The PCR products were purified on agarose gel and cloned into the pJet1.2 (CloneJet kit, K1231, Thermo Fisher Scientific). To tag tardigrade tubulin CDS with fluorescent proteins we employed NEBuilder® HiFi DNA Assembly Cloning Kit (E2621L, NEB).

Tardigrade β -tubulins and γ -tubulin were tagged with mScarlet. Corresponding tubulin CDS were amplified from above described pJet1.2-tubulin vectors by PCR using specific primers (Supplementary Table S3, designated as "HiFi"). The pLifeAct_mScarlet-i_N1 (a gift from Dorus Gadella⁶⁶; Addgene plasmid # 85056; <http://n2t.net/addgene:85056>; RRID:Addgene_85056) was linearized by NheI and BamHI that removed the LifeAct CDS. The linearized recipient plasmid and individual tubulin CDS were assembled using HiFi DNA Assembly creating fusion proteins with tubulins tagged on their C-terminus with mScarlet. The newly characterized *Hys. exemplaris* γ -tubulin obtained Genbank accession number OQ134936.

Tardigrade α -tubulins and ϵ -tubulin were tagged with mEGFP. First, mEGFP was amplified by PCR using specific primers (Supplementary Table S3, designated as "HiFi") for each tubulin CDS from pGEMHE-NLS-mEGFP (a gift from Melina Schuh⁶⁷; Addgene plasmid # 105527; <http://n2t.net/addgene:105527>; RRID:Addgene_105527). Second, each tubulin CDS was amplified by PCR using specific primers (Supplementary Table S3, designated as "HiFi") from above described pJet1.2-tubulin vectors. Third, pEGFP-C1 (Clontech) was linearized by NheI and HindIII which resulted in the removal of EGFP CDS. Finally, recipient plasmid backbone, mEGFP CDS and corresponding tubulin CDS were assembled using HiFi DNA Assembly creating fusion proteins with tubulins tagged on their N-terminus with mEGFP. All plasmids were verified by sequencing. pEGFP-Tub was originally from Clontech.

Transfection and confocal microscopy

The hTert-RPE1 and U87-MG cells were maintained in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) or Eagle's minimal essential medium (E-MEM), respectively, supplemented with 10 % (v/v) fetal bovine serum and 0.1 % (w/v) penicillin and 0.1 % (w/v) streptomycin. Cells were maintained in culture flasks (Falcon or Corning) at 37 °C and 5 % CO₂ in a humid atmosphere in an incubator and subcultured (passaged) every 2 to 3 days after obtaining 80 % to 90 % confluence. Cells were seeded on 18-well glass-bottom dishes (ibidi) one day before transfection and then transfected using Lipofectamine 3000 (Thermo) or JetOptimus (Polyplus) according to manufacturer's instructions. Cells were incubated in the incubator and visualized 24 h to 48 h post transfection.

Transfected cells were imaged using a Leica SP8 confocal microscope enclosed in an environmental chamber with constant temperature (36.9 °C), humidity (95 %) and 5 % CO₂ levels. Images were acquired using a 63x/1.40 N.A. oil objective. Filter and detector settings were optimised to minimise any possible bleed-through between fluorescence channels.

Fluorescence images were adjusted in Fiji⁶⁸. All acquired z-stack were processed using Maximum intensity projection and Brightness/contrast function. Only Tub1C1 was additionally processed using Subtract Background function with 150 pixels rolling ball radius.

REFERENCES

1. Fleming, J. F. & Arakawa, K. Systematics of tardigrada: A reanalysis of tardigrade taxonomy with specific reference to Guil et al. (2019). *Zool. Scr.* **50**, 376–382 (2021).
2. Jönsson, K. I., Borsari, S. & Rebecchi, L. Anhydrobiotic survival in populations of the tardigrades *Richtersius coronifer* and *Ramazzottius oberhaeuseri* from Italy and Sweden. *Zool. Anz. - A J. Comp. Zool.* **240**, 419–423 (2001).
3. Rebecchi, L., Altiero, T. & Guidetti, R. Anhydrobiosis: the extreme limit of desiccation tolerance. *Invertebr. Surviv. J.* **4**, 65–81 (2007).
4. Schill, R. O. & Fritz, G. B. Desiccation tolerance in embryonic stages of the tardigrade. *J. Zool.* **276**, 103–107 (2008).
5. Wełnicz, W., Grohme, M. A., Kaczmarek, Ł., Schill, R. O. & Frohme, M. Anhydrobiosis in tardigrades—The last decade. *J. Insect Physiol.* **57**, 577–583 (2011).
6. Czernekova, M. & Jönsson, K. I. Experimentally induced repeated anhydrobiosis in the eutardigrade *Richtersius coronifer*. *PLoS One* **11**, e0164062 (2016).
7. Schill, R. O. & Hengherr, S. Environmental Adaptations: Desiccation Tolerance. in *Water Bears: The Biology of Tardigrades* (ed. Schill, R. O.) 273–293 (Springer International Publishing, 2018).
8. Guidetti, R., Rizzo, A. M., Altiero, T. & Rebecchi, L. What can we learn from the toughest animals of the Earth? Water bears (tardigrades) as multicellular model organisms in order to perform scientific preparations for lunar exploration. *Planet. Space Sci.* **74**, 97–102 (2012).
9. Kaczmarek, Ł. *et al.* Staying young and fit? Ontogenetic and phylogenetic

- consequences of animal anhydrobiosis. *J. Zool.* **309**, 1–11 (2019).
10. Arakawa, K. Examples of extreme survival: tardigrade genomics and molecular anhydrobiology. *Annu. Rev. Anim. Biosci.* **10**, 17–37 (2022).
 11. Hesgrove, C. & Boothby, T. C. The biology of tardigrade disordered proteins in extreme stress tolerance. *Cell Commun. Signal.* **18**, 178 (2020).
 12. Yagi-Utsumi, M. *et al.* Desiccation-induced fibrous condensation of CAHS protein from an anhydrobiotic tardigrade. *Sci. Rep.* **11**, 21328 (2021).
 13. Tanaka, A. *et al.* Stress-dependent cell stiffening by tardigrade tolerance proteins that reversibly form a filamentous network and gel. *PLOS Biol.* **20**, e3001780 (2022).
 14. Kasianchuk, N., Rzymiski, P. & Kaczmarek, Ł. The biomedical potential of tardigrade proteins: A review. *Biomed. Pharmacother.* **158**, 114063 (2023).
 15. Jørgensen, A., Kristensen, R. M. & Møbjerg, N. Phylogeny and Integrative Taxonomy of Tardigrada. in *Water Bears: The Biology of Tardigrades* (ed. Schill, R. O.) 95–114 (Springer International Publishing, 2018).
 16. Mayer, G. *et al.* Selective neuronal staining in tardigrades and onychophorans provides insights into the evolution of segmental ganglia in panarthropods. *BMC Evol. Biol.* **13**, 230 (2013).
 17. Rota-Stabelli, O. *et al.* Ecdysozoan mitogenomics: evidence for a common origin of the legged invertebrates, the Panarthropoda. *Genome Biol. Evol.* **2**, 425–440 (2010).
 18. Rota-Stabelli, O., Daley, A. C. & Pisani, D. Molecular timetrees reveal a cambrian colonization of land and a new scenario for ecdysozoan evolution. *Curr. Biol.* **23**, 392–398 (2013).
 19. Yoshida, Y. *et al.* Comparative genomics of the tardigrades *Hypsibius dujardini*

- and *Ramazzottius varieornatus*. *PLOS Biol.* **15**, e2002266 (2017).
20. Pollard, T. D. & Goldman, R. D. Overview of the Cytoskeleton from an Evolutionary Perspective. *Cold Spring Harb. Perspect. Biol.* **10**, a030288 (2018).
 21. Herrmann, H. & Strelkov, S. V. History and phylogeny of intermediate filaments: Now in insects. *BMC Biology* **9**, (2011).
 22. Goldstein, L. S. B. & Gunawardena, S. Flying through the *Drosophila* Cytoskeletal Genome. *J. Cell Biol.* **150**, F63–F68 (2000).
 23. Hering, L., Bouameur, J.-E. E., Reichelt, J., Magin, T. M. & Mayer, G. Novel origin of lamin-derived cytoplasmic intermediate filaments in tardigrades. *Elife* **5**, 1–18 (2016).
 24. Janke, C. & Magiera, M. M. The tubulin code and its role in controlling microtubule properties and functions. *Nat. Rev. Mol. Cell Biol.* **21**, 307–326 (2020).
 25. Walz, B. Molting in Tardigrada. A review including new results on cuticle formation in *Macrobiotus hufelandi*. in *Proceedings of the Third International Symposium on the Tardigrada* (ed. Nelson, D. R.) 129–142 (East Tennessee State University Press, USA, 1982).
 26. Gross, V. & Mayer, G. Neural development in the tardigrade *Hypsibius dujardini* based on anti-acetylated α -tubulin immunolabeling. *Evodevo* **6**, 12 (2015).
 27. Mayer, G., Kauschke, S., Rüdiger, J. & Stevenson, P. A. Neural markers reveal a one-segmented head in tardigrades (water bears). *PLoS One* **8**, e59090 (2013).
 28. Persson, D. K., Halberg, K. A., Jørgensen, A., Møbjerg, N. & Kristensen, R. M. Neuroanatomy of *Halobiotus crispae* (Eutardigrada: Hypsibiidae): Tardigrade brain structure supports the clade panarthropoda. *J. Morphol.* **273**, 1227–1245

- (2012).
29. Persson, D. K., Halberg, K. A., Jørgensen, A., Møbjerg, N. & Kristensen, R. M. Brain anatomy of the marine tardigrade *Actinarctus doryphorus* (Arthrotardigrada). *J. Morphol.* **275**, 173–190 (2014).
 30. Smith, F. W. & Jockusch, E. L. The metameric pattern of *Hypsibius dujardini* (Eutardigrada) and its relationship to that of other panarthropods. *Front. Zool.* **11**, 66 (2014).
 31. Schulze, C., Neves, R. C. & Schmidt-Rhaesa, A. Comparative immunohistochemical investigation on the nervous system of two species of Arthrotardigrada (Heterotardigrada, Tardigrada). *Zool. Anz.* **253**, 225–235 (2014).
 32. Zantke, J., Wolff, C. & Scholtz, G. Three-dimensional reconstruction of the central nervous system of *Macrobotus hufelandi* (Eutardigrada, Parachela): implications for the phylogenetic position of Tardigrada. *Zoomorphology* **127**, 21–36 (2008).
 33. Garriga, E. *et al.* Large multiple sequence alignments with a root-to-leaf regressive method. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **37**, 1466–1470 (2019).
 34. Findeisen, P. *et al.* Six subgroups and extensive recent duplications characterize the evolution of the eukaryotic tubulin protein family. *Genome Biol. Evol.* **6**, 2274–2288 (2014).
 35. Luallen, R. J. *et al.* Discovery of a natural microsporidian pathogen with a broad tissue tropism in *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *PLOS Pathog.* **12**, e1005724 (2016).
 36. Gaşiorek, P. & Kristensen, R. M. New marine heterotardigrade lineages (Echiniscoididae) from the tropics. *Eur. Zool. J.* **89**, 719–754 (2022).
 37. Ludueña, R. F. Possible roles of specific amino acids in β -tubulin isoforms in the

- growth and maintenance of neurons: novel insights from cephalopod mollusks. *Front. Mol. Neurosci.* **15**, (2022).
38. Wang, W. *et al.* Novel mutations involving β I-, β IIA-, or β IVB-tubulin isotypes with functional resemblance to β III-tubulin in breast cancer. *Protoplasma* **254**, 1163–1173 (2017).
 39. Gąsiorek, P., Stec, D., Morek, W. & Michalczyk, Ł. An integrative redescription of *Hypsibius dujardini* (Doyère, 1840), the nominal taxon for Hypsibioidea (Tardigrada: Eutardigrada). *Zootaxa* **4415**, 45 (2018).
 40. Brunak, S., Engelbrecht, J. & Knudsen, S. Prediction of human mRNA donor and acceptor sites from the DNA sequence. *J. Mol. Biol.* **220**, 49–65 (1991).
 41. Hebsgaard, S. Splice site prediction in *Arabidopsis thaliana* pre-mRNA by combining local and global sequence information. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **24**, 3439–3452 (1996).
 42. Yutin, N. & Koonin, E. V. Archaeal origin of tubulin. *Biol. Direct* **7**, 10 (2012).
 43. Zhao, Z. *et al.* Molecular evolution and functional divergence of tubulin superfamily in the fungal tree of life. *Sci. Rep.* **4**, 6746 (2015).
 44. Morek, W. *et al.* Redescription of *Milnesium alpigenum* Ehrenberg, 1853 (Tardigrada: Apochela) and a description of *Milnesium inceptum* sp. nov., a tardigrade laboratory model. *Zootaxa* **4586**, 35–64 (2019).
 45. Bertolani, R. & Kinchin, I. M. A new species of *Ramazzottius* (Tardigrada, Hypsibiidae) in a rain gutter sediment from England. *Zool. J. Linn. Soc.* **109**, 327–333 (1993).
 46. Hashimoto, T. *et al.* Extremotolerant tardigrade genome and improved radiotolerance of human cultured cells by tardigrade-unique protein. *Nat. Commun.* **7**, 12808 (2016).

47. Roszkowska, M. *et al.* Tips and tricks how to culture water bears: simple protocols for culturing eutardigrades (Tardigrada) under laboratory conditions. *Eur. Zool. J.* **88**, 449–465 (2021).
48. Li, G. & Moore, J. K. Microtubule dynamics at low temperature: Evidence that tubulin recycling limits assembly. *Mol. Biol. Cell* **31**, 1154–1166 (2020).
49. Turk, E. *et al.* Zeta-Tubulin is a member of a conserved tubulin module and is a component of the centriolar basal foot in multiciliated cells. *Curr. Biol.* **25**, 2177–2183 (2015).
50. Smith, F. W., Bartels, P. J. & Goldstein, B. A hypothesis for the composition of the tardigrade brain and its implications for panarthropod brain evolution. *Integr. Comp. Biol.* **57**, 546–559 (2017).
51. Stathatos, G. G., Dunleavy, J. E. M., Zenker, J. & O'Bryan, M. K. Delta and epsilon tubulin in mammalian development. *Trends in Cell Biology* **31**, 774–787 (2021).
52. Chang, P., Giddings, T. H., Winey, M. & Stearns, T. ϵ -Tubulin is required for centriole duplication and microtubule organization. *Nat. Cell Biol.* **5**, 71–76 (2003).
53. Møbjerg, N., Jørgensen, A., Kristensen, R. M. & Neves, R. C. Morphology and Functional Anatomy. in *Water Bears: The Biology of Tardigrades* (ed. Schill, R. O.) 57–94 (Springer International Publishing, 2018).
54. Roll-Mecak, A. The Tubulin Code in Microtubule Dynamics and Information Encoding. *Developmental Cell* **54**, 7–20 (2020).
55. Kamilari, M., Jørgensen, A., Schiøtt, M. & Møbjerg, N. Comparative transcriptomics suggest unique molecular adaptations within tardigrade lineages. *BMC Genomics* **20**, 607 (2019).

56. Mapalo, M. A. *et al.* The unique antimicrobial recognition and signaling pathways in tardigrades with a comparison across ecdysozoa. *G3 Genes, Genomes, Genet.* **10**, 1137–1148 (2020).
57. Mapalo, M. A., Stec, D., Mirano-Bafscos, D. & Michalczyk, Ł. *Mesobiotus philippinicus* sp. nov., the first limnoterrestrial tardigrade from the Philippines. *Zootaxa* **4126**, 411 (2016).
58. Perry, E., Miller, W. R. & Kaczmarek, Ł. Recommended abbreviations for the names of genera of the phylum Tardigrada. *Zootaxa* **4608**, 145 (2019).
59. Camacho, C. *et al.* BLAST+: architecture and applications. *BMC Bioinformatics* **10**, 421 (2009).
60. Sievers, F. *et al.* Fast, scalable generation of high-quality protein multiple sequence alignments using Clustal Omega. *Mol. Syst. Biol.* **7**, 539 (2011).
61. Mistry, J. *et al.* Pfam: The protein families database in 2021. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **49**, D412–D419 (2021).
62. Katoh, K. & Standley, D. M. MAFFT Multiple Sequence Alignment Software Version 7: Improvements in Performance and Usability. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* **30**, 772–780 (2013).
63. Nguyen, L.-T., Schmidt, H. A., von Haeseler, A. & Minh, B. Q. IQ-TREE: A Fast and Effective Stochastic Algorithm for Estimating Maximum-Likelihood Phylogenies. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* **32**, 268–274 (2015).
64. Lefort, V., Desper, R. & Gascuel, O. FastME 2.0: A Comprehensive, Accurate, and Fast Distance-Based Phylogeny Inference Program: Table 1. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* **32**, 2798–2800 (2015).
65. Littler, D. S., Hellebust, J. A., Litter, M. M. & Craigie, J. S. *Handbook of Phycological Methods: Culture methods and growth measurements.*

- (Cambridge University Press, 1973).
66. Bindels, D. S. *et al.* MScarlet: A bright monomeric red fluorescent protein for cellular imaging. *Nat. Methods* **14**, 53–56 (2016).
 67. Clift, D. *et al.* A method for the acute and rapid degradation of endogenous proteins. *Cell* **171**, 1692-1706.e18 (2017).
 68. Schindelin, J. *et al.* Fiji: an open-source platform for biological-image analysis. *Nat. Methods* **9**, 676–682 (2012).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The project was supported by a grant No.: UJEP-SGS-2021-53-003-2 within the Student grant competition at UJEP (K.N.F., M.C., J.S., S.V.). The authors acknowledge the assistance provided by the Research Infrastructure NanoEnviCz (Project No. LM2018124) and the project Pro-NanoEnviCz (Reg. No. CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/16_013/0001821 and CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/18_046/0015586), supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic and the European Union European Structural and Investments Funds in the frame of the Operational Programme Research Development and Education (K.N.F., M.C., J.S., J.M., S.V.). Studies have been conducted in the framework of activities of BARg (Biodiversity and Astrobiology Research group, Ł.K.). The research leading to these results has also received funding from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (A.B and C.N.). We acknowledge the support of the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation to the EMBL partnership, to Centro de Excelencia Severo Ochoa and to the CERCA Programme of Generalitat de Catalunya (A.B and C.N.).

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization, S.V.; Methodology, K.N.F., A.B., M.C., J.S., S.V.; Investigation, K.N.F., A.B., S.V.; Resources, S.V., C.N., M.C., Ł.K., J.M.; Formal analysis, K.N.F., A.B., J.S., S.V.; Writing Original Draft, S.V., Writing – Review & Editing, K.N.F., A.B., M.C., J.S., C.N., Ł.K., J.M., S.V.; Funding acquisition, C.N., Ł.K., J.M., S.V.; Supervision, C.N., J.M., Ł.K., S.V.; Supervision of the project, S.V.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Further information and requests for resources and reagents should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the corresponding author (stanislav.vinopal@ujep.cz). Recombinant DNA generated in this study is available upon request from the corresponding author. The datasets generated and/or analysed during the current study are included in this published article (and its Supplementary Information files) and are also available in the repository Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7528263>). All sequenced tubulin CDS of *Hys. exemplaris* were uploaded to GeneBank (tHe-Tub1A1, OQ282841; tHe-Tub1A2, OQ282842; tHe-Tub1C1, OQ282843; tHe-Tub2C, OQ282844; tHe-Tub2D2, OQ282845; tHe-Tub2D3, OQ282846; tHe-Tub2D4, OQ282847; tHe-Tub3, OQ134936; tHe-Tub5, OQ282848)

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1. Phylogenetic analysis of tubulin homologs found in tardigrades

(a-f) Phylogenetic trees computed from alignments of tardigrade tubulin homologous sequences with Findeisen et al. ³⁴ dataset. (a, c, e) Minimum evolution method (FastMe). (b, d, f) Maximum likelihood method (IQ-TREE). (a-b) UJEP dataset - full tubulin sequences, (c-d) CRG dataset - full tubulin sequences, (e-f) CRG dataset - extracted tubulin domains only. All phylogenetic trees are rooted by an archeal tubulin-like group. The legend describes color coding. See also Supplementary data 1 and Supplementary data 2.

Figure 2. Identification of tardigrade tubulin isoforms

(a-b) Different visualizations of an identical phylogenetic tree computed from an alignment of the curated tardigrade tubulin dataset with Findeisen et al. ³⁴ dataset. (a) Maximum likelihood method (IQ-TREE). (b) Maximum likelihood method (IQ-TREE), non-tardigrade tubulins branches collapsed and branch lengths ignored to simplify visualization. Grey circles indicate SH-aLRT test score⁶³. The legend describes color coding. See also Supplementary data 3 and Supplementary Table 1.

Figure 3. Specific sequence signatures of tardigrade α -tubulins

(a) An alignment of the C-terminal region of tardigrade α -tubulins. Orange boxes indicate individual isoforms. Note the very C-terminus. (b) Specific AA differences among tardigrade α -tubulin isoforms. See also Supplementary data 4.

Figure 4. Specific sequence signatures of tardigrade β -tubulins

(a) An alignment of the C-terminal region of tardigrade β -tubulins. Red boxes indicate individual isoforms. (b) Specific AA differences among tardigrade β -tubulin isoforms. See also Supplementary data 4.

Figure 5. Tardigrade tubulins localize to microtubules or to the centrosomes in mammalian cultured cells

(a) A schematic of a mammalian cell with microtubules and the centrosome. (b) Maximum intensity projections (MIP) of living U87-MG cells overexpressing indicated constructs. Human EGFP-tagged α -tubulin (TUBA1B) used as a control. Note that all tardigrade β -tubulins localize to microtubules. c) MIP of living hTert-RPE-1 cells overexpressing indicated constructs. Note that tardigrade γ - and ϵ -tubulins localize to the centrosome (magenta arrows). Scale bars 10 μ m.

TABLES

Table 1. List of tardigrade transcriptomes and genomes used in this study

Species	Data type	Abbreviation	Reference/GeneBank Accession number
<i>Echiniscooides cf. sigismundi</i>	transcriptome	tEs	Kamilari et al. ⁵⁵
<i>Richtersius cf. coronifer</i>	transcriptome	tRc	Kamilari et al. ⁵⁵
<i>Echiniscus testudo</i>	transcriptome	tEt	Mapalo et al. ⁵⁶
<i>Mesobiotus philippinicus</i>	transcriptome	tMp	Mapalo et al. ⁵⁶
<i>Milnesium tardigradum</i> (now <i>Milnesium inceptum</i>)	transcriptome	tMt	GFGZ00000000.1
<i>Paramacrobotus richtersi</i>	transcriptome	tPr	GFGY00000000.1
<i>Hypsibius exemplaris</i>	genome/annotated CDS	tHe	Yoshida et al. ¹⁹ MTYJ00000000.1
<i>Ramazzottius varieornatus</i>	genome/annotated CDS	tRv	Hashimoto et al. ⁴⁶ BDGG00000000.1